

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

The mechanical properties of carbon fibers were evaluated by testing with a tensile testing apparatus for mono-filament. Two types of carbon fibers; HS type fiber and HM type fiber, were used in the present study. More than fifty specimens were tested for each group of the fiber. Furthermore, the degradation of the strength of carbon fiber by molten aluminum was investigated by testing the fibers extracted from Al-CF composites fabricated with liquid phase hot pressing. The tensile strength of carbon fibers depended on the fiber diameter. The tensile strength of carbon fibers increased with decreasing the fiber diameter. The elastic modulus of carbon fibers also depended on the fiber diameter. The data of the tensile strength of carbon fibers well agreed with the Weibull distribution and the tensile strength of carbon fibers depended on the specimen length. The tensile strength increased with decreasing the specimen length. The average tensile strength of carbon fibers decreased and the variability of the tensile strength of carbon fiber increased while kept in contact with molten aluminum.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibers have been considered as one of the most promising reinforcements for fiber strengthened composites. It is important to obtain reliable estimates of the mechanical properties of the fiber for predicting the strength of composites to be fabricated. For brittle materials, the Weibull distribution function¹⁾ has been most often employed for describing the fracture behaviors. It has been shown that the fracture stresses of brittle fibers, such as carbon fiber and silicon carbide fiber, well agree with the Weibull distribution function²⁾³⁾. Commercial carbon fibers can be classified into two groups; high strength (HS) type and high modulus (HM) type. In the present study, the mechanical properties of two types of carbon fibers were measured and treated by the Weibull analysis. Furthermore, the degradation behavior of carbon fibers by molten aluminum was also analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of commercial carbon fibers were employed in this study. The one is high strength (HS) type carbon fiber (T-300) and the other, high modulus (HM) type carbon fiber (M-40). Tensile testing was carried out with a table top type tensile testing apparatus for mono-filament. A specimen was mounted between grips of the apparatus with adhesive agent. Diameters of sample fibers were determined on enlarged photographs of the specimen. More than fifty specimens were tested for each group of carbon fiber. Specimens with 5 to 200 mm gauge length were tested to determine the dependence of gauge length on the tensile strength of the fiber. On the other hand, specimens with a constant gauge length of 20 mm were used for the other evaluations.

To investigate the degradation behavior of the HM type carbon fiber by molten aluminum, Al-CF composites were fabricated by liquid phase hot pressing with changing the holding time of hot pressing. Then, carbon fibers were extracted by dissolving the matrix with 10 % sodium hydroxide solution and the specimens of extracted carbon fibers were tension tested.

The Weibull Distribution

According to the Weibull distribution function, the failure probability at a stress σ is given as follows:

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-(\sigma - \sigma_u)^m / \sigma_o) \quad (1)$$

where σ_u is the location parameter, σ_o , the scale parameter and m , the Weibull modulus.^u It is usual to apply the Weibull distribution function in a two parameter form assuming σ_u is zero. So, a two parameter form was employed in this study. From equation^u (1), the following relationship is derived.

$$\ln \ln(1/(1 - F(\sigma))) = m \ln \sigma - \ln \sigma_o \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) gives a linear relationship between $\ln \ln(1/(1-F(\sigma)))$ and $\ln \sigma$ and the slope of the curve is equal to m . The average fracture stress is given by the following equation.

$$\bar{\sigma}_b = \sigma_o \Gamma(1/m + 1) \quad (3)$$

The Weibull distribution function also gives the following relationship.

$$\bar{\sigma}_b = \sigma_o ((l/d)^{-1/m}) \Gamma((m+1)/m) + \sigma_u \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_b$ is the average fracture stress, l , the specimen length and d , the specimen diameter. From equation (4), the following equation,

$$\ln \bar{\sigma}_b = -1/m \ln(l/d) + \ln \sigma_o + \ln \Gamma(1/m + 1) \quad (5)$$

is derived. Equation (5) gives the linear relationship between $\ln \bar{\sigma}_b$ and $\ln l$, or $\ln(l/d)$, where (l/d) is the specimen aspect ratio, that is, the length to diameter ratio.

RESULTS

The relationship between the tensile strength and the fiber diameter of the HS type carbon fiber with a gauge length of 20 mm is shown in Fig. 1 and the same relationship of the HM type carbon fiber is shown in Fig. 2. The tensile strength of carbon fibers depended on the fiber diameter. The tensile strength had a tendency to increase with decreasing the fiber diameter. The arithmetical mean of the tensile strength of the HS type carbon fiber was 3.01 GPa and that of the HM type carbon fiber, 2.44 GPa. The arithmetical mean of the diameter of the HS type carbon fiber was 6.8 μ m and that of the HM type carbon fiber, 7.1 μ m. The relationship between elastic modulus and the fiber diameter for the HS type carbon fiber is shown in Fig. 3 and that for the HM type carbon fiber, in Fig. 4. In both cases, the elastic modulus also has a tendency to increase with decreasing the fiber diameter. The ranges of distribution of the data of the HM type carbon fiber are wider than those of the HS type carbon fiber. Especially, the data of elastic modulus of the HM type carbon fiber distribute much wider than those of the HS type carbon fiber.

The Weibull plot of the data of fracture stress of carbon fibers is shown in Fig. 5 for the HS type fiber and in Fig. 6 for the HM type carbon fiber. In both cases, the data showed a linear relationship and agreed with the Weibull

distribution. The average fracture stress by the Weibull analysis was 2.92 GPa for the HS type fiber and 2.41 GPa for the HM type fiber and the Weibull modulus, m , was 5.7 for the HS type carbon fiber and 4.1 for the HM type carbon fiber. The relationship between $\ln b$ and the specimen length for the HS type carbon fiber is shown in Fig. 7 and that for the HM type fiber, in Fig. 8. In both fibers, the fracture stress increased with decreasing the specimen length. However, the fracture stress of the specimens shorter than 5 mm showed a tendency rather downward.

The Weibull plot of the data showing the degradation of the tensile fracture strength of the HM type carbon fiber while kept in contact with molten aluminum is shown in Fig. 9. The curves of the Weibull plot shift to the lower strength side and the Weibull moduli decrease with time kept in contact with molten aluminum. Fig. 10 shows the changes in the average fracture stress of carbon fiber and the Weibull modulus while kept in contact with molten aluminum. The size of flaw corresponding to the average fracture stress was calculated and also plotted in Fig. 10.

DISCUSSION

It has been reported that the tensile strength of fibers depended on the fiber diameter⁴⁾. The tensile strength and elastic modulus of carbon fibers investigated in the present study also depended on the fiber diameter. However, the range of distribution of the data of elastic modulus of the HM type carbon fiber is wider than that of the HS type carbon fiber. The reason why the variability of the elastic modulus of the HM type carbon fiber is large is not clear.

In the Weibull plots of two types of carbon fibers, the Weibull modulus for the HM type carbon fiber is smaller than that for the HS type carbon fiber corresponding to the wide spread distribution of the measured data. It is important that the fracture strength depends on the specimen gauge length. The tensile strength of carbon fibers changes 5-8 % when the gauge length varies 10 mm. Therefore, the gauge length should be appended to the tensile strength value of fibers. The tensile strength values obtained in the present study are lower than the catalogue values. It may be attributed to the different gauge length used. The shorter the specimen length, the higher the tensile strength of the fiber. However, the tensile strength of the fiber specimen shorter than 5 mm does not invariably increase due to the error in specimen alignment. In most cases, the average tensile strength of carbon fibers by the Weibull analysis differs from the arithmetical mean value. The difference between two values depends on the mode of distribution of the data.

It is known that the fracture of brittle fibers as carbon fibers initiates from the flaws at the fiber surface. The relationship between the fracture stress and the flaw size of a fiber is given by the following equation⁵⁾,

$$\sigma_b = 0.56 K_{IC} a^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

where K_{IC} is the fracture toughness and a , the defect size. As the value of fracture toughness of carbon fiber is not available, the value for graphite⁶⁾, 1.2 MPa $m^{-1/2}$, was adopted here. The flaw sizes corresponding to the average fracture stresses were estimated by the above equation. The obtained flaw sizes were plotted in Fig. 10. Compared with the fiber diameter, the estimated flaw sizes are considered to be reasonable. The degradation of carbon fibers by molten aluminum is attributable to the formation of reaction products between carbon fiber and matrix, Al_4C_3 , at the fiber surface⁷⁾. As shown in Fig. 10, the flaw size increases with time. It may correspond to the growth of Al_4C_3 crystals at the surface of carbon fiber while kept in contact with molten aluminum.

Fig. 1 Relationship between tensile strength and diameter for the HS type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 2 Relationship between tensile strength and diameter for the HM type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 3 Relationship between elastic modulus and diameter for the HS type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 4 Relationship between elastic modulus and diameter for the HM type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 5 Weibull plot of fracture stress for the HS type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 6 Weibull plot of fracture stress for the HM type carbon fiber. (Gauge length: 20 mm)

Fig. 7 Dependence of gauge length on fracture stress for the HS type carbon fiber.

Fig. 8 Dependence of gauge length on fracture stress for the HM type carbon fiber.

CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of carbon fibers were evaluated and the degradation behavior of carbon fiber by molten aluminum was investigated. The following conclusions were obtained.

- (1) The tensile strength of carbon fibers depends on the gauge length. The tensile strength of carbon fibers varies 5-8 % per 10 mm change in gauge length. Therefore, a gauge length should be appended to the tensile strength value.
- (2) The tensile strength of carbon fibers decreases and simultaneously the Weibull modulus decreases with time kept in contact with molten aluminum.

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Fig. 9 Weibull plots of fracture stress for the HM type carbon fiber while kept in contact with molten aluminum at 953 K.

Fig. 10 Changes in average fracture stress, Weibull modulus and flaw size corresponding to Fig. 9.